

VALIDATION RESULTS FROM VAMAS AND ISO ROUND ROBIN EXERCISES

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ABSTRACT

Significant progress is being made in the international harmonisation of standard test methods for fibre-reinforced plastic composites. One major influence of European Union CEN standardisation is the requirement that data on the precision of the test method shall be included in new standards. These data are obtained in round-robin (RR) validation exercises, which give the repeatability (r) and reproducibility (R) of the test method. In this paper the basic principles involved in round-robin exercises are outlined. Data are reported from several round-robins organised by ISO, VAMAS or nationally to support future international standardisation.

INTRODUCTION

The existing requirement for evidence of the precision of a test method for inclusion in International Standards Organisation (ISO) standards has been reinforced by:-

- increasing implementation of quality systems, such as CEN.ISO 9000,
- test laboratory accreditation, such as that by NAMAS in the UK,
- certification or materials qualification requirements and
- support to legally enforceable "Directives" within the European Union by Comité Européen de Normalisation (CEN) standards.

Substantial effort has been made in recent years to harmonise existing standards [1] for composite materials for the basic test methods. The harmonisation process is reliant on substantial pro-active support from standard bodies and their supporting experts to overcome both minor and major differences, which have arisen for historical reasons in spite of similar philosophy in each case. Progress on the tensile test for composites has allowed a RR exercise to be initiated on behalf of ISO.

The value of undertaking the harmonisation and validation work is shown by recent comments from Hercules [2] on the qualification of one fibre and resin combination as both a unidirectional (UD) tape and fabric. The cost was fifteen times greater for the ten specifications in use, for each product, than if a single specification existed. In future, it is hoped that the VAMAS (Versailles Project on Advanced Materials and Standards) pre-standards programme can be used to obtain early technical agreement on a recommended method that can then be submitted, with validation data, to ISO for formal standardisation. The second phase of the programme is supported by Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the United States, the United Kingdom and

EU, with other countries able to join particular projects. Fracture toughness and fatigue round-robins have been undertaken in Technical Working Area 5 on Polymer Composites. New projects, such as on the compression-after-impact test method, are under consideration.

In this paper the basic principles involved in round-robin exercises used to validate test methods are outlined. The procedures are illustrated by data from several recent and current RRS. The RRs were organised by ISO, VAMAS or nationally to support future standardisation.

VALIDATION EXERCISE PROCEDURES

ISO 5725 describes the procedure to be followed in validation exercises and is equivalent to ASTM E 691, except that the latter is slightly stricter on the removal of outlying data. The work involved in validation is very expensive and time-consuming for all materials. The advantage of being able to "design" the material with composites, leads to potentially endless permutations of material to be tested in order to ensure validation of the test method. A minimum of six or seven materials is needed to represent the most commonly available materials, with testing at eight or more sites depending on the number of levels (materials) used. The number of exercises run can be reduced by undertaking them at the highest level (eg ISO) and by targeting the most important test methods. The relevant definitions are given below.

Table 1. Precision definitions from ISO 5725

Precision is defined as "the closeness of agreement between mutually independent test results obtained under stipulated conditions". Two measures of precision, "repeatability - r" and "reproducibility - R", are necessary to describe the variability of a test method.	
REPEATABILITY CONDITIONS:- same method identical material same laboratory same operator same equipment short interval of time	REPRODUCIBILITY CONDITIONS:- same method identical material different laboratories different operators different equipment
The repeatability value is defined as the value below which the absolute difference between two single test results obtained under repeatability conditions may be expected to lie within a probability of 95%. Similarly, the reproducibility value R refers to a 95% probability level.	

A more practical statement of precision in BS 4415 on tensile testing of paper and board is:-

"Repeatability - The difference between the two single test results found on identical test material by one operator using the same apparatus within a short period of time interval will exceed the repeatability value on average not more than one in twenty instances of the normal operation of the test." Reproducibility is similarly worded but for ".....between two single and independent results found by two operators working at different sites on identical material.....".

One major point of interest is that in round-robins for destructive tests the material are not "identical" and the material variability is included in the RR results. A selection of round-robins in progress or recently completed is listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Recent Round-Robin Exercises

Test Method	Organiser
Fracture Toughness Static - Mode I, Mode II, Fatigue - Mode I, Mode II,	ASTM ESIS VAMAS
Tension	ISO, ASTM, JIS
Plate-twist (in-plane shear)	NPL
Fatigue - tension, flexure	VAMAS
Test Panel Manufacture	NPL

TEST PANEL MANUFACTURE

An essential and preliminary stage of the testing and evaluation of a material is the preparation of the test panel for subsequent specimen fabrication. The international standard ISO 1268 is currently being revised to cover preparation of test panels in a range of polymer composites manufactured by the appropriate method. Part 1 of the standard gives the general principles, with Parts 2 to 10 covering particular materials and process routes (eg injection moulding, compression, thermoforming, filament winding etc). Part 6 will cover test panels made from pre-impregnates by the autoclave route. Similar standards have been drafted in the ASTM and EN Aerospace series. A recent UK round-robin used a single batch of prepreg purchased by NPL. Sufficient prepreg for 4 panels at three thicknesses was distributed direct to the participants by the materials supplier.

Panels were fabricated at eight sites according to prEN (Aerospace) 2565 and sent to NPL for evaluation [3]. The quality of the panels was assessed by ultrasonic C-scans, weight fractions, microscopic sections and a range of mechanical tests (see below). The ultrasonic scan showed only a 2 to 3 dB variation in attenuation over each panel except when a release ply was used. The results of the other analyses are given in Table 3. Data are not included for the 1 mm and 2 mm panels from one site which were curved, without explanation, rather than flat.

Table 3. Precision data associated with test panel manufacture

Property - Panel Thickness	Mean	Repeatability r	s.d. of r /Mean (%)	Reproducibility R	s.d. of R /Mean (%)
Weight - 1mm	69.3 %	2.44 %	1.4	8.44 %	4.4
Fraction - 2mm	67.1 %	5.43 %	2.5	6.54 %	3.5
- 5mm	69.2 %	3.41 %	1.5	4.35 %	2.2
ILSS - 2mm	104 MPa	10.0 MPa	3.4	22.4 MPa	7.6
V-Notched - 5mm Shear	125 MPa	7.21 MPa	2.1	9.79 MPa	2.8
Flexure - 2mm					
E ₁₁	122 GPa	6.81 GPa	2.0	31.30 GPa	9.1
E ₂₂	7.96 GPa	0.575 GPa	2.6	1.89 GPa	8.5
σ ₁₁	1780 MPa	246 MPa	4.9	321 MPa	6.4
σ ₂₂	151 MPa	39.9 MPa	9.4	56.0 MPa	13.2

The results suggest that a good quality test panel can be made consistently at different sites using the autoclave manufacturing route, which should provide a suitable foundation for data generation. Little is known regarding other process routes or the next stages of specimen preparation (eg machining, tabbing). Both these areas would benefit from similar investigations.

PLATE TWIST TEST FOR IN-PLANE SHEAR MODULUS

This test method has recently been proposed as an ISO new work item supported by validation data. A simple plate specimen is supported on two corners of one diagonal of the plate and loaded by the two points on the opposite diagonal. A practical difficulty with the test has been the positioning of the loading points; which are normally in-board of the actual corner. This mis-positioning leads to an error of several percent in the value of G_{12} . A correction factor has been numerically determined and validated experimentally [4].

NPL has recently conducted a validation exercise [5] at eight sites using six materials representing a range of polymer composites (UD glass-fibre/epoxy, SMC (sheet moulding compound), woven glass-fibre/epoxy, random glass-fibre/polypropylene, injection moulded glass-fibre/nylon and UD carbon-fibre/epoxy). One set of plates for each material was circulated to all participants to reduce material scatter as the test involves only small elastic strains. Typical sets of data are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Unidirectionally reinforced glass-fibre/epoxy data from all sites

Figure 2. Random glass-fibre/polypropylene data from all sites

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VAMAS ROUND-ROBINS

TENSILE AND FLEXURAL FATIGUE

The VAMAS fatigue RR covered in Part 1 [8] both tensile and flexural fatigue of six unidirectional materials. Participants were requested to follow a "core" test procedure based on a review of the then current static and fatigue standards. The starting point of standard ISO specimens for the ultimate (static or short term) failure strengths was not available. Difficulties arose because a wide range of ultimate strengths was measured by participating laboratories and some values, such as for GRP in tension, were below the first fatigue stress level set at 80% of the ultimate strength measured by NPL. In an attempt to reduce the scatter, specimens with end-tabs already attached were supplied. This approach did not solve the problem, suggesting that other factors (eg grip design, grip pressure, specimen and machine alignment) needed checking.

It is clear that prior validation of the "static" test method, as now proposed, so that the level of reproducibility expected was known could have saved time in the fatigue project. The fatigue data were found to be more consistent for tensile loading than for flexural loading [9]. The data have been used to support an ISO new work item proposal, to complement an existing item on flexural fatigue. It is hoped that in completing the current work, together with tests in other modes where interest has been shown (compression, fully reversed, transverse); there will be increased emphasis on fatigue aspects such as the effect of frequency, stress range, data presentation, etc..

Collated data are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 for tensile fatigue of glass-fibre/epoxy and carbon-fibre/epoxy, respectively. The agreement is less good for flexural loading as shown in Fig. 5. The extrapolation of the fatigue data in Fig 3 agrees best with the higher static strength measured at a rate equivalent to the fatigue test loading rate.

Figure 3. Tensile S-N fatigue data for glass-fibre/epoxy at five sites

Figure 4. Tensile S-N fatigue data for carbon-fibre/epoxy at three sites

Figure 5. Flexural S-N fatigue data for glass-fibre/epoxy at two sites

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The delamination crack growth programme closely followed the ASTM procedures for both static and fatigue loading conditions in Mode I and Mode II. Drafting of test methods was being undertaken cooperatively between ASTM, JIS and ESIS (European Structural Integrity Society). While there is agreement on the basic configuration of the test there remain difficulties over some important detailed aspects (eg method of pre-cracking).

The results showed lower scatter for Mode I compared to Mode II [10]. For Mode I tests hinges were recommended in preference to "T" tabs. Mode I pre-cracking was recommended prior to conducting Mode II tests; but no effect was found for Mode I tests. The preferred method of analysis of the several tried was the compliance based method, which allowed for fibre-bridging of the delamination crack. No finalised VAMAS report is available yet for the delamination crack growth under cyclic loading conditions, but the UK results are recorded in [11].

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

Recognition of the advantages gained from ISO standards together with the catalytic action of the standardisation activities in CEN has enabled progress on harmonisation and validation of test methods. To achieve the desired results requires considerable effort in the drafting of standards and the organisation of validation round-robins. Although significant work needs to be undertaken based on a high level of international collaboration and consultation, there will be considerable financial and practical benefits to the composites industry [2]. It should be noted that research is still required to optimise existing tests and to develop new test methods.

Further round robins led by the UK with invited international participation on compressive, flexural, interlaminar shear and $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile shear test methods are using CEN/ISO parallel processed drafts. These drafts were based on existing ISO, ASTM, JIS and other recommended methods.

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REFERENCES

1. G D SIMS, "International standardisation of coupon and structural element test methods", ECCM-Composites: Testing and Standardisation 2, Hamburg, (1994).
2. Hercules press release
3. J L LESNIAREK-HAMID, W R BROUGHTON, H C JONES and G D SIMS, "Report on Round Robin Programme on Draft Standard - Aerospace - Preparation of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Resin Panels for Test Purposes (prEN 2565)", NPL Report DMM(A)128, (1994).
4. G D SIMS, W NIMMO, A F JOHNSON and D H FERRISS, "Analysis of Plate-Twist Test for In-Plane Shear Modulus of Composite Materials", NPL Report DMM(A)54, (1992).
5. W NIMMO and G D SIMS, "Validation of plate-twist shear test for composites", NPL Report DMM(A)156, (1994).
6. CEN/ISO/DIS 527 - 5, Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Test conditions for unidirectional fibre-reinforced plastic composites.
7. P T CURTIS "CRAG test methods for the measurement of engineering properties of fibre reinforced plastics" 3rd Edition RAE TR 88012, (1988).
8. G D SIMS, "A VAMAS round-robin on fatigue test methods for polymer matrix composites. Part 1, Tensile and flexural tests of unidirectional material", NPL Report DMM(A)180, (1989).
9. G D SIMS, "Interim VAMAS report on Part 1 of polymer composites fatigue round-robin", NPL Report DMM(A)69, (1995).
10. R.KHOSHRAVAN and C.BATHIAS, "Delamination tests of DCB and ENF composite specimens in Mode I and Mode II", Annual Report of VAMAS WG5, (1990).
11. W R BROUGHTON, "VAMAS round-robin project on polymer composite delamination in Mode I and Mode II; Cyclic loading", NPL Report DMM(A) 47, (1992).